

Exploring Salient Features Influencing Repeat Visit Intention of Young Costumers in Shopping-Malls

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Abstract:- Main aim of the study is to explore significant factors that will ensure customers to visit again to the shopping mall for future purchases. In this context, convenience and safety, variety of retail stores, perceived value, tangible facilities, sensory stimulations, social recreation, employee behavior and repeat visit intention were the constructs identified after diligent literature review. This research is exploratory in nature focusing young Saudi customers. 350 forms both online and hardcopy were distributed. Effectively, 220 observations were found normally distributed to be included in final analysis, after excluding unfilled forms, missing data-points, and outliers. Likert scale was used to measure fifty items. Exploratory factor analysis performed for grouping of variables and data reduction. Reliability measures satisfactorily undertaken. Convergent validity and discriminant validity of the constructs was statistically established. Multiple regression applied to comprehend the impact analysis of extracted variables and test hypothesis thereof. Conclusively, perceived value (*veracious*), sensory stimulation (*vibes*) and employee behavior (*savoir-faire*) originated as positively significant impact factors, on repeat visit intention (*convivial*) of the young Saudi customers. The results were found to be in tandem with recent studies. Academicians can conduct cluster analysis for customer segmentation with bigger sample size across age, income, and regions. This study recommends mall managers to develop competitive differentiated marketing strategies to hold their customer's footfall for a longer duration. Limitations include difficulty communicating and accessing the respondents and self-financing.

Keywords:- Shopping malls, retail marketing, variety of retail stores, perceived value, repeat visit intention

I. INTRODUCTION

Shopping malls (SMs) are generally referred to as an organized cluster of retail outlets under one roof offering a variety of product assortments (Berman, Evans, 2001). Such organized retailers cooperate to use the same infrastructure attracting customer foot falls and compete for the share of wallets and/or time (Mägi, 2003). Shopping mall also refers to stores located in a single building, planned, designed, and built for retailing and retail-related activities; are managed as a single unit by an institutional center management (Levy and Weitz, 2007). SMs or shopping plaza nowadays are preferable venue to buy a wide range of branded as well as not-so-branded consumer products. Needless to mention an extensive array of products available for almost all age groups and gender in SM are grocery items, kitchen utensils, fashionable garments, footwear, accessories, books and stationery, personal care products, computer and electronics, home-appliances, fitness equipment, travel essentials, etc. Shoppers can expect all these products of high quality at an affordable price. SMs now offers many value-added services to enrich its buyer's leisure time such as coffee shops, movie theatres, food courts with comfortable seating area, gaming zones, children's playing area, prayer rooms, parking area, elevators, etc, and even five-star luxurious hotels. SMs are gaining economic as well as cultural importance in many countries. One of the largest listed companies in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) is *Arabian Centres* responsible for development and operation of around 4300 stores in 11 major cities hosting 109 million visitors each year; Mall of Arabia, Mall of Dharhan, Al Hamra, and Nakheel Mall are one of the luxurious properties operated by Arabian Centres. To mention a few other unrivaled malls in KSA are Kingdom Centre, Mode Al Faisaliyah, Red Sea Mall, Al Rashid, Mall of Arabia, Granada Center, Lu-Lu, Makkah Mall, Panorama, Centria, etc. All these lifestyle centers display unique designs of architectural marvels and are strategically located at the intersection of accessible roads. Majority of malls are ornated with mix of luxurious global brands such as Aigner, Aidan Mattox, Amouage, Bershka, Bizou, Cirawmag, Gianfranco-Ferre, Hublot, Jomalone,

L'occitane-en-province, Oak-Leaves, Swarovski, Tory Burch, Tumi, Vacheron-Constantin, Yauatcha, Zimmerli, etc. With an ambition to deliver strong roots to its vibrant society, the Vision 2030 blueprint of KSA provides guidelines for overall national transformation, featuring its shift of focus from oil sector to non-oil sector. It encourages investments in real estate (capital spending) primarily to develop housing, education, health, tourism, industries, and retail sectors with major concerns to improve gross domestic production from 5% to 10% by 2030. *Saudi Arabia General Investment Authority* (SAGIA) grants license for foreign direct investments in various sectors including real estate, which provides for minimum investment of 30 million Saudi Riyals (SAR) for establishments outside the border of Mecca and Medina, requiring to develop within five years and allowing up to 100% foreign investments into wholesale, retail, and e-commerce. However, instructing the foreign companies to train 30% of Saudi nationals annually and locate them in senior management positions in the first five years. In 2016, a property management company was listed in stock exchange (Tadawul) named *Real Estate Investment Traded Funds* (REITF), whose primary objective is to invest in construction industry. Its investors will receive the prescribed percentage of net profit in cash. Another program hatched in KSA is the *Public Investment Fund* (PIF) to unlock international financially viable projects in priority sectors. Its portfolio investment has achieved a growth of assets from worth 507 billion SAR to a whopping 1500 billion SAR in year 2015. International strategic investment partnerships under PIF are Russian Direct Investment Fund, Blackstone Infrastructure Fund, Uber, Jio Platforms, Reliance Retail, Investment Program in Brazil, Babylon Health, French Private Equity Investments and many more. Such infrastructure policies of KSA unquestionably attracts investments in developing shopping malls as part of real estate sector and turn out to be magnetic source of income in Saudi Arabia's economic gravity. Issuance of foreign investment licenses in the retail sector has grown 347% annually in KSA over the past few years. Although capital investments in shopping mall construction is associated with many financial obstacles with long-term profitability but only when maintained in a thoughtful manner. Such a vast lifestyle potential scenario and strong base of the young Saudi population with a median age of 29 years, persuades us to conduct this study. Youth visit malls more frequently than other age groups satisfying their self-congruity and functional congruity (Massicotte et al. 2011).

II. IMPORTANCE OF CULTIVATING BUYING EXPERIENCE AT SHOPPING MALLS

The interior glance of the mall is enhanced with bright lighting, soothing music, fragrance, colorful product assortments and signboards about product shelf-brackets, spacious layout, durable flooring, and lively décor on special occasions to mark it as an exceptional spot. Remarkably, all these features differentiate shopping malls from each other to compete in market (Kwortnik and Ross, 2007). To be precise, the challenge lies in probing elements responsible for customer motives visiting shopping malls that helps devising retail strategies. Shopping motives are not always product related but also cultivates an opportunity for

retailers for strategic segmentation of customers by providing socio-recreational benefits (Sipho Makgopa, 2016), this was well hypothesized by Tauber (1972) and today has become an essential field of investigation in retail marketing. The research about key dimensions of consumer experiences is just another way of understanding why they visit malls for shopping. In marketing context, Gupta and Vajic 2000 (as cited by Adrian Palmer, 2010) defined *customer experience*, that the service provider creates many sensory elements to induce customers to interact with the functional utility of the product or brand. Likewise, a stimulating environment is created in the malls to entice customers to acquire knowledge about the available products, which lingers them for a future purchase. An ultimate attitude can be developed by integrating process quality, brand relationships, and interpersonal relationships *mediated through* sequencing of tangible cues, impulses to evaluate the cues, and consistency of perceptions of the customer to become part of his memorable *experience* (Adrian Palmer, 2010). A summary analysis from the mall management perspective, it was found that there are multiple paths to enhance retail shopper experiences such as managing consumer behavior (how consumers encode, retain and retrieve retailer cues), promotion (in-store and online), pricing (conforming quality), merchandise (product variety in optimal quantity), supply chain management (channel structure), location (travel time for customers and proximity to other stores) and retail metrics (use of data to formulate and execute marketing strategies). Key challenge is to hold on profitable customers to create long-term loyal advocates (Grewal et al. 2009). In another theoretical refinement (Puccinelli et al. 2009) about consumers' buying perspective, a few key domains were identified i.e. consumer goals (consonance with product variety and retail environment), memory (price sensitivity is significant while retrieval process), involvement (it can be high or low at different times and affects consumers' subjective search experience), attitude (context and messages play an important role), affective processing (a positive mood induced by music or free promotions to enthruse customers open to new products), atmospherics (retail environmental stimuli impel customer's product information search, sensory experiences and patronage intentions), and consumer attributions and choices (consistent accords with the retail employees determines the attributional valence). One of the studies, in Bloomington (USA), conveys that there is a subtle influence of consumer decision-making styles (Sproles and Kendall, 1986) of adult mall shoppers in different mall contexts. It indirectly governs the activities engaged during mall visits of the shoppers (Wesly et al. 2006). In a huge lack of literature regarding behavior of Saudi customers, many such abstract dynamics need be unearthed to contribute accordingly. Arises the need for the proposed study.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

This section aims to focus on criteria based on which customers can decide for repeat visit in the mall. A scale was developed and validated in a hierarchical factor structure model to measure service quality of retail stores. This study conducted in southeastern part of America concluded that customers evaluate retail service quality as a higher order factor with some basic dimensions i.e., physical aspects, reliability, personal interaction, problem solving and policy (Dabholkar et al. 1996). One of the past structural models, composed of 35 items, established that when shopping mall customers are exposed to wide variety of tenant mix and appealing ambience, design and layout, they become highly excited for more purchasing and their desire to stay for a longer time in the mall is also elongated; and an amplified patronage proves to be an ultimate outcome (Wakefield and Baker, 1998). In a comparative study about buying at shopping street and shopping mall in Vienna, composed of 30 items, it was revealed that the amount of money and time spent in one visit by the customers in a shopping mall was fairly more than spent in shopping street. Also, that tenant mix and merchandise value have a most significant direct impact on the overall attractiveness of the malls, along with an atmosphere (Teller C. and Reutterer T., 2008). A model study, conducted on Indian consumer's shopping motivations in shopping malls, validated two major factors – utilitarian (convenience, economic, achievement) and hedonic (enjoyment, gratification, idea, aesthetics, role, social) composed of 24 items (Patel V. and Sharma M., 2009). In a study conducted in South Africa, the price, behavior of shop staff and in-store advertisements play positively significant role to cause consumer's impulsive buying, followed by coupons and in-store displays (Tendai M., Chipunza C., 2009). A validation study composed of 23 items, in Montreal, affirmed that location, store atmosphere, promotional pricing, range of products available under one roof and number of brands, styles and quality offered in a particular product category, significantly contributes to an overall 'mall image' which in turn develops considerable attitude, patronage and recommendation among customers (Chebat et al. 2010). The role and social interaction among Indian consumers were found to have a significant impact on mall behavior, but aesthetics, escape, flow, exploration, and convenience were not. All seven factors were composed of 27 items (Arpita Khare, 2011). Attractiveness (or ambience) was the foremost influencing factor followed by service quality, entertainment, aesthetics, convenience, and product variety as per regression output, in enhancing customer satisfaction; and positive word-of-mouth as resultant outcome in Saudi Arabia (Khalaf, 2012). Convenience and quality of customer service have most positive significant impact on customer satisfaction in malls of Hong Kong, followed by rewards, mall environment and quality of retailers. When customers are satisfied, they spread positive word-of-mouth among their connections; this was validated in a study composed of 21 items (Wong et al., 2012). Promotional events and tenant mix, i.e., marketing focus was evidenced to be most significant among shoppers' experience in Dubai. Along with an interplay of ambience, physical infrastructure, and convenience (Harvinder Singh

and Sanjeev Prashar, 2013). Four components, with 47 items in retail customer experience were explored, wherein store convenience emerged as having strongest association followed by store atmosphere, relationship orientation, and store staff (Bagdare S. 2013). Leisure had the largest contribution followed by joy, distinctiveness and mood validated as in overall customer experience dimensions composed of 12 items, in a study conducted in Indore (Bagdare and Jain, 2013). A structural equation model exhibited that mood plays a significant mediating role to influence re-patronage, time and money spent by Muslim consumers in Malaysia. And that the mall atmospheric cues such as music, color and salesperson behavior positively enhance mood of the consumers irrespective of age-groups, all composed of 33 items (Osman et al. 2014). A study in Romania, about shopping centers, found that variety of product assortment contributes most to augment customer satisfaction, along with décor, communication, service, and pricing (Abrudan and Dabija, 2014). Renovation proved to be the most essential precursor to makeover the mall atmosphere, which indirectly influences an improved consumer spending through enhanced satisfaction by way of utilitarian values, as established in a study conducted in North America composed of total 16 validated items (Chebat et al. 2014). Out of the conceptual heterogeneity of customer shopping mall experiences, the four constructs were studied namely seductive, functional, social recreation and social scene, to validate a 16-item scale. And concluded that there is a significant impact of social recreation and social scene on mall loyalty through mall equity but unexpectedly not the functional (Gilboa et al. 2016). In a three-phase confirmatory study, a holistic nature of VISUALSCAPE dimensions was validated as second order, composed of 16 items related to shopping malls, which have positively significant impact on the affective and behavioral components of the overall consumer experience (taken as the second order construct) with reasonably high correlation values (Bagdare and Roy, 2016). Among the attraction factors influencing the mall visits, in Columbia, it was validated that eco-natural design (such as green spaces, display of vegetation) also have significant impact in addition to product variety and quality, mobility and accessibility, additional services and entertainment, physical environment, maintenance, and security, composed of 25 items (Ortegon-Cortazar L. and Royo-Vela M. 2017). One of the structural models fit composed of 31 items establishes that patronage intentions are highly dependable on customer satisfaction derived mainly from internal shop environment and in-shop emotions duly supported with interaction of customers with staff and merchandise assortments (Terblanche, 2017). Seven factors of shopping malls were explored, namely service experience, internal environment, convenience, utilitarian, acoustic, proximity, and demonstration, as selection criteria of Indian consumers (Kushwaha, T. et al. 2017). In-store customer experience has a significant direct impact on customer satisfaction but indirectly on loyalty through satisfaction. Such customer experience scale, composed of 32 items, was validated on four dimensions namely cognitive, affective, social, and physical (Bustamante and Rubio, 2017). Wider mix of retail tenants and overall ambience play an important role in increasing visits of customers at a shopping mall followed by entertainment

factor, revealed in a study in Spain. An 18-item validated model exhibited that such repeat visits put significant influence on the purchase intentions of the customers (Calvo-Porrall and Levy-Mangin, 2018). The retail store environment is very impactful on the purchase decision of customers, and they also feel better regarding perceived value for their purchases, but surprisingly the sales promotion offered at the retail stores are insignificant. According to a study conducted in Malaysian retail market with 24 item statements (Hanaysha J.R. 2018). A structural model exhibited a moderate influence of product assortment and perceived quality, social networking, aesthetics and architectural design, convenience, promotional offer, retail tenant mix, prices of products and role enactment on mall patronage frequency was found through a strong attitude, composed of 40 items in a study in Nigeria (Idoko et al. 2019). A scale of five constructs – design and aesthetics, service options, convenience, and safety (most important), service employees and utilitarian value – was validated as determinants of shopping mall attraction in Kenya (Kiriri P.N. 2019). Shopping malls attract repeat visits of their customers especially if it were successful in generating a memorable shopping experience to them. On similar lines a longitudinal study conducted in France and USA, across the three contexts of mall, online and in-store, validated a memory scale of consumers experience on four dimensions, namely, attraction, structure, affect and social, composed of 14 items (Flacandji M. and Krey N., 2020). An integrated model fit factor study composed of 27 items, established that the perceived atmosphere, created by the individual stores in the malls, mediates to put an impact on mall loyalty of the consumers spending more with seeking hedonic experiences compared to utilitarian experiences (Vilnai-Yavetz et al. 2021). A systematic content review of 40 years of research on various dimensions of mall attributes was carried out, since 1970s, capturing the mall image whilst comparing American and European school of mall studies. Subsequently, a descriptive mall image model was

developed comprising of 20 items in 8 dimensions, namely – location/access, parking, ambience, retail offer, leisure offer, facilities, atmosphere, and self-congruity – broadly along tangible and intangible traits (Gomes and Paula, 2017). According to a study conducted in Greece, there exists a moderate influence of trust in purchasing grocery brands, but the impact of trust is different for different product category brands (Sarantidou P.P., 2018). Most of the studies known are in democratic environment whereas KSA is supposed to be culturally conservative society; however, consumer needs are usually same in nature. KSA provides entirely different geographical regions for retail chain operators, thus providing a unique market environment for this study.

This review of literature adapted 50 investigative items classified among seven constructs as independent variables and one dependent variable as shown in *appendix-i*, affirming the content validity of the same. Based on above literature review, following constructs for this study have been identified, developed, and hypothesized:

H₁: Convenience and safety (CS) provided by malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₂: Variety of retail stores (VS) available in malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₃: Perceived value (PV) gained from shopping in malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₄: Tangible facilities (TF) of malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₅: Sensory stimulation (SS) felt in malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₆: Social recreation (SR) experienced at malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

H₇: Employee behavior (EB) of malls positively influences repeat visit intention (RIN) of young customers

Fig. 1: Theoretical Framework

IV. OBJECTIVES

- To assess behavioral aspects of young customers visiting malls.
- To recognize dimensions that are acceptable for young customers to visit again in the mall.
- To comprehend the extent of relationship among factors influencing repeat visit intention of young customers.
- To explore significant factors influencing the repeat visit intention of young customers.
- To understand the intensity of influence of factors on repeat visit intention of young customers.
- To recommend mall managers to devise competitive strategies that can retain customers for a longer time.
- To understand how to improve the overall shopping experience of customers visiting malls.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive and exploratory in nature. Convenient sampling is adopted to collect the data online as well as in person from the Al-Kharj region of KSA. 350 forms both online (Google Forms) and hardcopy were distributed out of which total 283 forms were received. 240 forms found to be usable for further analysis excluding unfilled forms and missing data-points. Another 20 cases were canceled, being identified as outliers based on Z-scores. Effectively, 220 observations were found normally distributed to be included in final analysis. The sample size is fair enough according to Hair Anderson et al. 1995a and Comrey 1973. All 50 items were measured on a five-point Likert Scale (score 1 for least and 5 for highest agreeableness). Reliability measures such as Cronbach’s alpha for all items satisfactorily undertaken. Data reduction technique applied containing exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to recognize the most appropriate dimensions acceptable for young customers to visit the mall again. EFA was functional as it allows exploring relatively significant factors from a large set of latent constructs, as stated by Pett, Lackey et al. 2003; Swisher, Beckstead et al. 2004; Thompson 2004; and Henson and Roberts 2006. EFA is also suitable for scale development based on common factors

identified as stated by Hurley, Scandura et al.; Hayton, Allen et al. 2004. Convergent validity and discriminant validity applied to test the degree of relatedness as well as unrelatedness of the variables. Multiple regression applied to comprehend the impact analysis of extracted variables on repeat visit intention of respondents and test hypothesis framed. MS-Office 365 and SPSS-21 employed for all data analysis.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS

Based on various confirmatory research studies, most relevant items were identified and marginally edited (without losing the key intention) to be grasped by the respondents. Fifty item statements were transformed into eight constructs for data collection as shown in [appendix-i](#), which also qualifies the content validity of the constructs selected. Demographic profile is shown [appendix-ii](#) comprising 79.58% of male and 20.42% female respondents with average age of 27 years, spending approximately 128.80 SAR average (weighted) per visit in SMs. 82% of respondents visit the mall at least once a week, 10.8% twice and 6.7% thrice a week. 43.75% respondents reported household income up to 100,000 SAR, 29.1% reported up to 150,000 SAR, 11.25% reported up to 200,000 SAR and 15.9% reported above 200,000 SAR. 350 forms, both online (google forms) and hardcopy, were distributed, on convenience sampling basis, out of which total 283 forms were received. Effectively, 220 observations were found normally distributed to be included in final analysis, after excluding unfilled forms, missing data-points, and outliers. Approximate normality of the data (n=220) is shown in [appendix-iii](#) passing Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests (p>0.05) shown via histogram ([appendix-iii-a-b](#)). Group descriptive statistics of all extracted factors can be seen in [appendix-iv](#). Initial correlations, as shown in [appendix-v](#), found to be moderate and important but significant between perceived value (PV), sensory stimulation (SS) and employee behavior (EB) with repeat visit intention (RIN) before extraction. This allows to conduct EFA further as per Kraiser, 1958.

Table 1: Correlations after EFA

N=220	afterEFA_CSF1_2q	afterEFA_VSF2_2q	afterEFA_PVF3_2q	afterEFA_SSF5_3q	afterEFA_SRF6_3q	afterEFA_EBF7_3q	afterEFA_RINF8_3q
afterEFA_CSF1_2q	1						
afterEFA_VSF2_2q	.013 .845	1					
afterEFA_PVF3_2q	.005 .940	.134*	1				
afterEFA_SSF5_3q	-.013 .848	.270**	.274**	1			
afterEFA_SRF6_3q	.108 .112	.068 .316	.076 .262	.284**	1		
afterEFA_EBF7_3q	.078 .252	.210**	.259**	.331**	.198**	1	
afterEFA_RINF8_3q	.109 .107	.188**	.284**	.326**	.181**	.404**	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

A satisfactory and significant association of repeat visit intention (RIN) with perceived value (PV), sensory stimulation (SS) and employee behavior (EB) is still evident after EFA as shown in Table-1.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	0.715	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1039.000
	Df	153
	Sig.	.000

Output in Table-2 shows measure of Kaiser-Meyer-Ohlin (KMO>0.50), which is considered satisfactory to analyze EFA output further as stated by Netemeyer, Bearden et al. 2003. Bartlett's test of sphericity indicates that the

matrix is not an identity matrix having p-value less than 0.05. This also ensures the sampling adequacy suitable for factor analysis further, as stated by Tabachnick and Fidell 2001, and Netemeyer, Bearden et al. 2003.

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrix ^a (as per SPSS output)	Factor Loadings (lambda)						
	SS	RIN	EB	SR	PV	CS	VS
Q2-SS-F5 (The interior design of the mall attracts my attention.)	0.774						
Q3-SS-F5 (I feel the atmosphere in the mall very cheerful and refreshing.)	0.685						
Q4-SS-F5 (The air quality and bright lighting inside the mall makes my shopping more pleasurable.)	0.807						
Q4-RIN-F8 (I will always say favorable things about this shopping mall to all my friends, family, and colleagues.)		0.638					
Q5-RIN-F8 (How likely are you to come here again and buy something?)		0.847					
Q6-RIN-F8 (I will definitely continue to shop more at this mall in future.)		0.818					
Q1-EB-F7 (The staff of this mall have good knowledge about the products available.)			0.730				
Q3-EB-F7 (The behavior of the staff of this mall is very friendly and makes me feel comfortable in my shopping.)			0.728				
Q5-EB-F7 (The staff of this mall is always ready to help me.)			0.733				
Q2-SR-F6 (The mall is a good place to make new friends or re-unite with old ones.)				0.775			
Q3-SR-F6 (The mall is a good place to meet people we know.)				0.847			
Q4-SR-F6 (The mall is a fun place to spend time with family and friends.)				0.641			
Q5-PV-F3 (I am sure that the products I buy from the malls are always of high quality.)					0.841		
Q6-PV-F3 (The products that I buy from the mall are always reliable.)					0.848		
Q1-CS-F1 (I am able to reach the mall easily from the highway or road.)						0.885	
Q2-CS-F1 (I am able to reach to the mall from my home very easily and quickly.)						0.868	
Q2-VS-F2 (In the mall, I can easily notice many retail shops such as for clothing, footwear, grocery, beauty, accessories, and sports.)							0.769
Q3-VS-F2 (In the mall, I can easily find shops for food, coffee, bakery and ice-cream.)							0.756
EIGEN VALUE	4.05	1.765	1.711	1.497	1.301	1.235	1.074
CUMULATIVE VARIANCE (%)	11.563	22.759	33.003	43.211	52.679	61.608	70.151
CRONBACH'S ALPHA (reliability measure)	0.713	0.749	0.665	0.668	0.736	0.718	0.490
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a							
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.							

Table-3 reportsextraction of factors through EFA. Reportingitem loadings in its own grouped factor withrespective Eigen values, cumulative percentage, and

Cronbach's alpha values for internal consistency of extracted factors.Coefficients were suppressed at 0.50 limit during each rotation.

Fig. 2: Scree Plot for Extracted Factors

Table 4: Construct Validity

Dimensions (retained)	AVE (based on lambda figures given in Table-3)	Square Root of AVE	Composite Reliability
SS (I.V.)	0.5731833	0.757088	0.8004
RIN (D.V.)	0.597859	0.773213	0.8146
EB (I.V.)	0.533391	0.73033	0.7742
SR (I.V.)	0.576305	0.75914	0.8011
PV (I.V.)	0.7131925	0.84450	0.8325
CS (I.V.)	0.7683245	0.8765	0.8689
VS (I.V.)	0.581449	0.76252	0.7353

The human brain is a complex web of emotions; still some overlapping responses need be separated statistically. For this purpose, construct validity (Campbell and Fiske, 1959) of the scale is demonstrated in Table-4.

Further, multiple regression (enter method) was performed to test the hypothesis (H₁, H₂, H₃, H₅, H₆ and H₇):

Table 5: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.490 ^a	.240	.219	1.78465	1.668

a. Predictors: (Constant), afterEFA_EBF7_3q, afterEFA_CSF1_2q, afterEFA_VSF2_2q, afterEFA_SRF6_3q, afterEFA_PVF3_2q, afterEFA_SSF5_3q
 b. Dependent Variable: afterEFA_RINF8_3q

Regression model output in Table-5 exhibits an overall impact of 49% of all six predictors put together and 21.9% after adjusting inflated values of all predictor upon RIN.

Table-6-ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1.	Regression	214.233	6	35.706	11.211	.000 ^b
	Residual	678.399	213	3.185		
	Total	892.632	219			

a. Dependent Variable: afterEFA_RINF8_3q
 b. Predictors: (Constant), afterEFA_EBF7_3q, afterEFA_CSF1_2q, afterEFA_VSF2_2q, afterEFA_SRF6_3q, afterEFA_PVF3_2q, afterEFA_SSF5_3q

Table-6 exhibits that overall multiple regression model is significant (p<0.05).

Table 7: Coefficients^a

Model (multi-variate regression output as per SPSS)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		Hypothesis (Supported or Rejected)
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
(Constant)	3.525	1.290		2.733	.007			
afterEFA_CSF1_2q	0.079	0.058	0.082	1.354	0.177	0.981	1.020	H ₁ (Rejected)
afterEFA_VSF2_2q	0.110	0.116	0.060	.955	0.341	0.908	1.101	H ₂ (Rejected)
afterEFA_PVF3_2q	0.183	0.075	0.154	2.441	0.015	0.891	1.123	H ₃ (Supported)
afterEFA_SSF5_3q	0.142	0.061	0.160	2.348	0.020	0.768	1.302	H ₅ (Supported)
afterEFA_SRF6_3q	0.039	0.045	0.055	.867	0.387	0.895	1.117	H ₆ (Rejected)
afterEFA_EBF7_3q	0.290	0.067	0.282	4.296	0.000	0.830	1.204	H ₇ (Supported)

a. Dependent Variable: afterEFA_RINF8_3q

Table-7 exhibits regression results and impact analysis. Non-existence of multi-collinearity.

VII. RESULTS

Noticeably, the correlation between factors went down after applying EFA (Table-1), but remained significant and moderate, compared to initial correlation status. An important and significant positive relationship is found, in accordance with Tabachnick and Fidell 2001, between employee behavior (40.4%), sensory stimulation (32.6%) and perceived value (28.4%) for money spent by customers and repeat visit intention of customers. There exists no association between convenience and safety dimension with repeat visit intention, but significant association enrolled with variety of stores (18.8%) and social recreation (18.1%), however low. Factor analysis (Table-3) applied through principal component analysis (PCA) method emanated seven factors that had Eigen value more than one. Since, there is no prior theoretical model exists in the context of Saudi retail environment, PCA should be adopted for factor extraction as suggested by Gorsuch 1983 and Pett, Lackey et al. 2003. After twelve rotations, items eliminated gradually based on either low to moderate communalities (0.50) or low loadings or cross loadings. Varimax rotation method was applied, which is an orthogonal rotation process, developed by Thompson, 2004. The cumulative contribution of all factors upto 70% was quite satisfactory. As depicted in Table-3, commonly used multiple criteria for factor retention includes analyzing the cumulative percentage of all factors (should be at least 60% in humanities as per Pett, Lackey et al. 2003), eigen value (>1, Kaiser 1960) and Scree plot (interpretation is subjective based on datapoint break-up as suggested by Cattell 1966), this is suggested by Hair, Anderson et al. 1995a. Overall Cronbach's value for reliability of all 18 items extracted was 0.761 for extracted factors as shown in Table-3 which was very well satisfactory except variety of stores (VS), however this factor didn't show up any impact even after regression. The internal consistency of each dimension is quite good and above 0.60 (Bagozzi, 1988) except the factor named VS. Highest overall alpha for internal consistency achieved at 0.790, if CS, VS and SR excluded. Strikingly, none of the items related to tangible facilities (TF) were able to load anywhere during rotations, hence hypothesis (H₄) rejected at this stage itself. By way of convergent validity, a threshold measure is achieved i.e., AVE should be more than 0.50 and

composite reliability be more than 0.70, which is statistically observed for each factor (Table-4). Moreover, by way of discriminant validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), the square root of AVE of the latent factors (Table-4) is higher than the highest correlation between the constructs (40.4) as shown in Table-1. Hence, construct validity of the scale used to measure intent of factors is statistically established. Table-5 exhibits the regression model in which R-square value of 0.240 depicts that the model explains 24% of the variance in RIN due to changes in predictors. In Table-5 value of Durbin Watson test is below 2.5 which indicates that independent variables are not highly auto-correlated (Durbin Watson, 1951). The reporting of ANOVA in Table-6 was also found significant (0.000) at F=11.211 for all predictors; in other words, the predictors are significantly associated with repeat visit intention (RIN). The problem of multi-collinearity does not exist as the tolerance values are well above 0.10 standards and the variance inflation is also under the acceptable limits of 3 (Hair et al. 1995). This indicates that predictor variables are not mutually highly correlated, the individual effects sustained and this multivariate regression model (Table-7) is numerically accurate in forecasting outcome variable. Table-3 shows that only two items have been extracted for the factor PV (H₃) which indicates a weaker construct, but the loading values are more than 0.50 which is an added advantage, according to Costello and Osborne 2005. Additionally, Table-7 exhibits that independent variable PV (H₃) significantly predicted RIN, F(6, 219)=11.211, p<0.05, which proves that PV plays significant role in shaping RIN (B=0.183, p<0.05). Hence, hypothesis (H₃) supported. Table-3 shows that three items have been extracted for the factor SS (H₅) which indicates an acceptably stronger construct and the loading values are also more than 0.50, thus quite satisfactory as per Costello and Osborne 2005. Additionally, Table-7 shows that independent variable SS (H₅) significantly predicted RIN, F(6, 219)=11.211, p<0.05, which confirms that SS plays significant role in shaping RIN (B=0.142, p<0.05). Hence, hypothesis (H₅) supported. Table-3 shows that three items have been extracted for the factor EB (H₇) which indicates an acceptably stronger construct and the loading values are also more than 0.50, thus quite satisfactory as per Costello and Osborne 2005. Additionally, Table-7 also implies that

independent variable EB(H₇) significantly predicted RIN, $F(6, 219)=11.211$, $p<0.05$, which demonstrates that EB plays significant role in shaping RIN ($B=0.290$, $p<0.05$). Hence, hypothesis EB(H₇) supported. The multi-variate regression results explicitly demonstrate positive impact of PV, SS and EB on RIN. Moreover, the significant factor after regression also needs be labeled based on key characteristics of the variables as a matter of convention (Taherdost et al. 2020). Labelling of the constructs is subjective and inductive process (reflecting conceptual intent as per Pett, Lackey et al. 2003). Therefore, for the purposes of this study, major factors PV, SS, EB, and RIN are hereby labeled as VERACIOUS, VIBES, SAVOIR-FAIRE, and CONVIVIAL respectively, in order to be differentiated parsimoniously. Nonetheless, CS (H₁), VS (H₂), and SR (H₆) have been unsuccessful in placing any significant impact on RIN, so ultimately rejected.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study reveals that three significant predictors that will make the re-visit (CONVIVIAL) of the young Saudi customers to the mall possible and those identified are perceived value (VERACIOUS), sensory stimulation (VIBES), and employee behavior (SAVOIR-FAIRE). Sensory stimulation (*vibes*) hereby refers to the soothing internal atmosphere that makes the visitors in the mall much more comfortable and cheerful by way of bright lighting, display of products and interior design. It is herein evident that the physical sensation created in the malls have significant impact in creating an overall positive customer experience and henceforth customer's willingness to visit again to the mall (*convivial*). This is in accordance with the studies conducted by Gajanayeke et al. (2011), Osman et al. (2013), Bagdare, Roy (2016), Ortegon-Cortazar L., Royo-Vela M. (2017) that confirms a positive association in formation of customer attitude and visualscape in the mall. This could be ascribed to the fact that customers gaze for changed attractive surroundings in the mall while shopping. Physical stimulus plays an embarking role in creating sensational vibes in consumer's mind and probability of increased spending can be enhanced. Perceived value (*veracious*) hereby refers to the good value for money that customers feel in buying products, by making use of attractive discounts or sales promotions offered in the malls, which eventually proven to be of good quality as well as reliable. It is herein evident that the young Saudi customers receives good value for money for the products that they buy from the shopping malls being considerably of high quality as well as reliable. The perception of receiving value in spending money in the malls has positive and significant influence is hence established. Makgopa S. (2016), Hanaysha J.R. (2018) and Tjandra C., Muqarrabbin A.M. (2019) also reported that perceived value of shopping from the malls plays a significant influence on the purchase decision of the customer and hence in time translates in repeat visit intention (*convivial*). Employee behavior (*savoir-faire*) refers to social know-how. In a retail context it is the ability of the employees, say a sales representative or a manager, to interact with the customers. The staff in the mall not only have appropriate knowledge about the products available but are also willing to resolve customer problems

in most friendly manner (*convivial*). In this regard, it is also evident that young Saudis are happy with the knowledge of the products and helping behavior of the service staff working in shopping malls. A number of researchers support the same. Interaction with staff has proven to have major impact on re-patronage intention of customers (Terblanche, 2017). Employee services have a significant and positive impact on shopping mall attractiveness (Kiriri, 2019) which eventually performs in repeat visit intention (*convivial*) of the customer. The quality of customer service has considerable impact on customer satisfaction, which further motivates them to spread positive word of mouth (Wong et al. 2012). This study contributes academically by filling the knowledge gap in Saudi context through establishing factors influencing repeat visit or enhanced loyalty of young Saudi customers. This study was a modest attempt to establish a relationship between evident factors, as above, and its impact on repeat visits of young customers to shopping malls.

IX. DISCUSSION

Socialization in terms of shopping with friends and exploration in terms of discovering new things in the market found to be major factors determining shopper's patronage in Enugu metropolis (Okoro et al. 2019). Young Saudi like to meet friends in malls but do not expose high social activity with family or friends, may be due to their conservative approach when out of the home. Moreover, Saudi customers surely like to spread word of mouth and agree continue shopping from malls repeatedly in future, as is evident in this study and in tandem with past studies (Calvo-Porrall et al. 2018; Vilnai-Yavetz et al. 2021). Open access reports that retail rental in KSA has fallen down in the year 2021 due to COVID impact. Furthermore, that they are not at all carried away with tangible facilities available in malls and perceive as bare minimum such as number of check-out counters, sign-boards, escalators, or toilet facilities (Can F.G. et al. 2016). Unlike results of this study, it is confirmed that tangible benefits (products, ambience, and leisure activities) and intangible benefits (customer care, recommendations) do have positive association with increased frequency of customer visits (Adholiya A. et al. 2019). Saudi consumers prefer to buy from specific store for a specific purchase in a mall, Lebanese consumers prefers shopping malls for socializing activities and UAE consumers value the internal attributes like anchor stores in shopping malls while their visits (Koksal M.H. 2020). Still, the respondents duly notice but are not much impressed with the variety of tenant mix offered in shopping malls, maybe due to homogenization of merchandise in other malls (De Lisle, 2005). In this study respondents seemed indifferent with variety of products available which is unlike studied in the year 2012 in Jeddah (Khalaf, 2012). Yet, variety of choices of products or merchandise assortment available greatly influences repeat shopping-oriented customer loyalty indicating repeat footfall thereby (Aliagha et al. 2015). In this study convenience and safety are referred to car parking facility and security concerns, but respondents were indifferent towards it (Teller et al. 2008) and do not have considerable impact, as they rarely face any parking difficulty or safety issues. Due to the strategic location of

the malls in Al-Kharj region the customers are not much worried about distance or accessibility issues, and of course the incredible supply of oil. Saudi Arabia is well known for its strict legal environment, so safety inside the mall is not a big concern for Saudi customers. However, convenience and tangible or aesthetic dimensions of the malls have positively significant impact on customer purchase intention (Badar, et al. 2018).

X. MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Buying from shopping malls receives threat from rapid-fast growth of e-commerce anywhere. Nowadays social media advertisements' dimensions such as its informativeness, entertainment, credibility and perceived value employ proven impact on customer's purchase intention (Al Haddad et al. 2021). The unorganized retail sector will always remain traditionally competitive against organized retailing, despite in any developed nation like KSA. This study reveals that only 17% of customers visit mall twice or thrice a week. Challenge before mall management is not only to build a unique image of the mall but also to deliver sustainable competitive advantage to its customers. And this is a long marathon effort on daily basis looking forward the intensity of competition in retail sector in KSA with an influx supply of global brands to occupy space. The strategic managers of these lifestyle centers require an immediate attention to freeze, unfreeze and refreeze the retail strategies to pacify aspiring needs of young Saudis. Mall operators need to devise plans to let customers spend more time and money that creates an exciting buying environment besides revenue generation. Shopping mall management should gradually learn to adopt service differentiation strategies such as maintaining soothing atmosphere, product pricing based on bulk buying, maintaining variety of product inventory, establishing anchor stores, organizing family entertainment activities, selling beverages and snacks on spending point system, waste management, embrace technology, medical safety, cordial distribution network, employee training for a faster and timely customer service to all store tenants, if possible, based on customer feedback without disturbing their exploration time. Each of the backstage management activities adds a drop of satisfaction to the ultimate customer in the front. The lifecycle of shopping centers (Lowry J.R. 1997) is another educative issue in mall management. In KSA, strategist must not allow its mall to reach maturity stage and should prolong the accelerated development stage wherein rentals are high, advertising is moderate, minor modification required, retail strategies are aggressive, but the amount of shopper traffic increases steadily. Mall retailers must focus on improving this shopper traffic steadily and maintain high customer relationship through its trained employees. Such efforts would ensure a higher number of visits from customers per week. Mall managers have limited resources and must use them to gain patronage from their customers. Additionally, keeping an eye on competitor malls may add learning units to develop a differentiated brand image and sustain footfall of its customers. Also enlightens the shopping mall management to invent distinguished services and focus on key components

identified herein. Never to ignore that customers have rational mind too while purchasing and so do young Saudis.

XI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

Young consumers are just one segment of customers undertaken in this study. Scope for further studies involve academicians and mall strategist to conduct comparative service differentiation studies, cluster analysis for customer segmentation, factor study of consumer preferences to buy shopping products or specialty products or convenience products at different shopping malls. Each factor may have separate studies across regions, age, and income brackets. Authors have imprinted their maximum efforts to identify key factors in this study that left may be due to non-accessibility of studies or language barriers. Approaching Saudi national was a tough task as an expatriate, so author distributed questionnaire through friends, colleagues, and references from wherever feasible. Only male consumers were easily approachable. Responses of the female respondents were taken from college students only through online mode. One of the colleagues, teaching Arabic language, was requested to translate the questionnaire from English to Arabic. So dual language questionnaire was distributed to respondents for easy comprehension. The authors were hesitant to converse with any Saudi national due to language barrier for this study. Extensive traveling for data collection was also not affordable; therefore, respondents were selected only from the Al-Kharj region of the Riyadh province.

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APPENDICES

Appendix-i-Questionnaire Content Validity

(Note: Shaded items below were not retained after extraction in this study)

Constructs	Q#	Item Statements (developing questionnaire)	Source (inspired/adapted/ from:) – reflecting Content Validity
Convenience & Safety (CS)– Independent Variable (I.V.)	Q1	I am able to reach the mall easily from the highway or road.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019)
	Q2	I am able to reach to the mall from my home very easily and quickly.	Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010)
	Q3	I can always find sufficient parking space for my car in the parking area.	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008)
	Q4	It is easy and quick to enter the mall from parking area.	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008)
	Q5	The opening hour of the mall is good for me.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q6	The security and safety of the mall is very good.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019)
Variety of Retail Stores (VS)– (I.V.)	Q1	I can find different variety of retail shops in the mall.	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Kirk L. Wakefield, Julie Baker, (1998); Kiriri Peter N. (2019); Ortegon-Cortazar L., Royo-Vela M. (2017)
	Q2	In the mall, I can easily notice many retail shops such as for clothing, grocery, footwear, accessories etc.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q3	In the mall, I can easily find shops for food, coffee, ice-cream etc.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019)
	Q4	In the mall I can also notice shops for recreation such as playing area for kids, gaming zone etc.	Kirk L. Wakefield, Julie Baker, (1998)
	Q5	In the malls, I can find international brand stores such as Apple, Samsung, Gucci, Starbucks, KFC, Nike etc.	Terblanche Nic S. (2017); Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010); Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q6	Mall is the best place to buy products for personal and family use.	Author
Perceived Value (PV) – (I.V.)	Q1	I feel that I get good value for money whenever I buy products from the mall.	Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010); Hanaysha J.R. (2018); Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	Q2	Malls always offer attractive discounts on available products.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019); Wong et al. (2012)
	Q3	I like to take advantage of the sales promotions offered at the mall such as discounts, gift vouchers and cash coupons.	Patel V., Sharma M. (2009)
	Q4	In the malls the price labels put on every product help save my time as well as money.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q5	I am sure that the products I buy from the malls are always of high quality.	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Wong et al. (2012); Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010)
	Q6	The products that I buy from the malls are always reliable.	Hanaysha J.R. (2018); Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
Tangible Attractiveness (TA)– (I.V.)	Q1	The mall I visit have sufficient walking space to move around easily.	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Ortegon-Cortazar L., Royo-Vela M. (2017); Wong et al. (2012)
	Q2	The sign-boards and directions in the mall help me search where the products are exactly placed.	Calvo-Porrall C., Levy-Mangin J.P. (2018)
	Q3	The mall I visit has good interior design such as colorful walls, floors, decoration, and bright lightings.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019); Patel V., Sharma M. (2009); Kiriri Peter N. (2019); Kirk L. Wakefield, Julie Baker, (1998); Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	Q4	The mall I visit has enough number of check-out counters and I don't have to wait for longer in the queue.	Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	Q5	In the mall I always find a separate	Author

		counter to keep my extra bags safely.	
	Q6	While shopping if it's my praying time, I can easily find prayer rooms to pray in the mall.	Author
	Q7	I can easily find clean toilet facilities in the mall.	Author
Sensory Stimulation (SS)– (I.V.)	Q1	I like to walk through the mall for a longer time.	Vilnai-Yavetz I., Gilboa S., Mitchell V. (2021); Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q2	The interior design of the mall attracts my attention.	Osman S., Ong S.F., Othman M.N., Khong K.W. (2014); Bagdare S., Roy S. (2016)
	Q3	I feel the atmosphere in the mall very cheerful and refreshing.	Michael Flacandji, Nina Krey. (2020); Bagdare S., Roy S. (2016); Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010); Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008)
	Q4	The air quality and bright lighting inside the mall makes shopping more pleasurable.	Terblanche Nic S. (2017); Kirk L. Wakefield, Julie Baker, (1998); Kirk L. Wakefield, Julie Baker, (1998); Ortegon-Cortazar L., Royo-Vela M. (2017); Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008)
	Q5	The display of the products and services in this mall makes me feel enthusiastic and curious.	Bustamante J.C., Rubio Natalia (2017)
	Q6	The mall I visit is always clean.	Hanaysha J.R. (2018)
Social Recreation (SR)– (I.V.)	Q1	I enjoy more with my friends in the mall.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q2	The mall is a good place to make new friends or re-unite with old ones.	Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	Q3	The mall is a good place to meet people we know.	Vilnai-Yavetz I., Gilboa S., Mitchell V. (2021)
	Q4	The mall is a fun place to spend time with family and friends.	Vilnai-Yavetz I., Gilboa S., Mitchell V. (2021)
Employee Behavior (EB) – (I.V.)	Q1	The staff of this mall have good knowledge about the products available.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019); Terblanche Nic S. (2017); Wong et al. (2012)
	Q2	Opinion of the staff is good for me to select products in the mall.	Bustamante J.C., Rubio Natalia (2017)
	Q3	The behavior of the staff of this mall is very friendly and makes me feel comfortable in my shopping.	Osman S., Ong S.F., Othman M.N., Khong K.W. (2014); Wong et al. (2012); Kiriri Peter N. (2019)
	Q4	The salesman of this mall guides me search the best products I want to buy.	Kiriri Peter N. (2019)
	Q5	The staff of this mall is always ready to help me.	Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
Re-visit Intention (RIN) – Dependent Variable(D.V.)	RIN1	How satisfied you are after shopping at this mall?	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Wong et al., (2012); Hanaysha J.R. (2018)
	RIN2	How would you rate your overall experience with shopping at this mall?	Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	RIN3	I like to come at this mall again and again to search various products available.	Ortegon-Cortazar L., Royo-Vela M. (2017); Idoko E.C., Ukenna S.I., Obeta C.E. (2019)
	RIN4	I will always say favorable things about this shopping mall to all my friends, family, and colleagues.	Wong et al., (2012); Chebat J.C., Michon R., Haj-Salem N., Oliveira S. (2014); Chebat J.C., Sirgy M.J., Grzeskowiak S. (2010)
	RIN5	How likely are you to come here again and buy something?	Teller C., Reutterer T. (2008); Calvo-Porrall C., Levy-Mangin J.P. (2018); Vilnai-Yavetz I., Gilboa S., Mitchell V. (2021); Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	RIN6	I will definitely continue to shop more at this mall in future.	Terblanche Nic S. (2017)
	RIN7	I would like to come again to this mall because of products available at reasonable rates.	Author

RIN8	I would like to come again to this mall because of availability of high-quality products.	Author
RIN9	I would like to visit again to this mall because I get value for money I spend.	Author
RIN10	I would like to come again to this mall because of its pleasant atmosphere.	Author

Appendix-ii-Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variables (n=240) including outliers		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	191	79.58
	Female	49	20.42
Age	20-25 yrs.	143	59.58
	25 - 30 yrs.	51	21.25
	30 - 35 yrs.	31	12.92
	Above 35 yrs.	15	6.25
Number of Visits per Week	1	198	82.5
	2	26	10.8
	3	16	6.7
Money Spent (per visit in Saudi Rial currency – SAR)	Upto 50	25	10.5
	Upto 100	54	22.5
	upto 150	49	20.4
	More than 150	112	46.6
Household Income (per annum in Saudi Rial currency – SAR)	upto 100,000	105	43.75
	100,000 to 150,000	70	29.1
	150,000 to 200,000	27	11.25
	Above 200,000	38	15.9

Appendix-iii-Tests of Normality of all Constructs (excluding outliers)

n=220 (excluding outliers)	Kolmogorov-Smirnova ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
totalbeforeEF Aallconstructs	0.055	220	0.200*	0.990	220	0.150

* This is a lower bound of the true significance.
 a Lilliefors Significance Correction

Appendix-iii-a-b-Tests of Normality of all Constructs

Appendix-iv-Group Descriptive Statistics of Extracted Factors						
Extracted Factors	N	Range	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
afterEFA_CSF1_2q	220	8.00	7.7682	.14051	2.08405	4.343
afterEFA_VSF2_2q	220	5.00	9.0909	.07377	1.09416	1.197
afterEFA_PVF3_2q	220	6.00	7.8227	.11490	1.70426	2.905
afterEFA_SSF5_3q	220	9.00	12.5000	.15308	2.27052	5.155
afterEFA_SRF6_3q	220	12.00	10.1773	.19243	2.85421	8.147
afterEFA_EBF7_3q	220	7.00	12.4591	.13225	1.96154	3.848
afterEFA_RINF8_3q	220	8.00	12.3591	.13611	2.01890	4.076
Valid N (listwise)	220					

Appendix-v-Initial Correlation Status before EFA(n=220; total 50 items in 8 constructs)									
		CSF1_bef foreEFA	VSF2_bef foreEFA	PVF3_bef foreEFA	TAF4_bef foreEFA	SSF5_bef foreEFA	SRF6_bef foreEFA	EBF7_bef foreEFA	RINF8_bef foreEFA
CSF1_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	1							
VSF2_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.188**	1						
PVF3_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.314**	.430**	1					
TAF4_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.311**	.473**	.391**	1				
SSF5_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.206**	.461**	.458**	.577**	1			
SRF6_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.181**	.238**	.235**	.344**	.421**	1		
EBF7_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.318**	.347**	.398**	.468**	.396**	.260**	1	
RINF8_bef foreEFA	Pearson Correlation	.268**	.475**	.551**	.454**	.533**	.220**	.485**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).